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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **OL**ive and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 5.4

Report on the online survey findings

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Executive Summary

The Work Package (WP) 5 aims to engage with the MED-GOLD community to assess and upscale the usability of pilot services developed in WP2-4 through an online survey and sectoral participatory workshops. In doing this, the MED-GOLD community was established in Task 5.1 (RD.1). In task 5.2 we designed an online survey and disseminated it to the MED-GOLD community (Deliverable 5.2). This report is intended as a companion document to deliverable 5.2, where we reported the survey design process.

In total, we received 174 responses, representing the views of current users (n=139) and non-users (n=35) of climate information and impact indicators. Based on the quantitative analysis of the MED-GOLD survey, the users were generally positive about the added value of the dashboard in Olive and wine sectors, and all agreed the dashboard provides the timescales and variables they need in their decision-making. They also agreed that the tool could help them with some critical decisions such as pest control, harvest planning and production estimation. However, they suggested the tool should be easier to use, which is exactly confirmed the result of the tool's added value assessment in previous task (2.4 and 3.4).

Regarding the Granudora.net, the respondents agreed the tool is accessible, and provide the information and timescales they need in their roles. Most users think that the tool could help them with better disease control, improve efficiency in their crop protection planning. In response to recommendations on increasing the tool's usability, they believe that multi languages availability on the tool could be more helpful. Details of the assessment and recommendations have been provided in details in section 6.

1. Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B, Table 1.1):

Table 1-1 project objectives

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

2. Impact

This deliverable aims to assess the usability of the tools developed in the MED-GOLD project. The provision of climate services may not necessarily lead to the desired outcome of increased productivity due to a variety of reasons and obstacles and the assessment could help us to identify such obstacles. The assessment of the climate service in the sector was done through an online survey and several sectoral participatory workshops and this deliverable analyses the results of the online survey.

Table 2-1 Expected impacts of the deliverable

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	X
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

3. Definitions

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 3-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate service	Climate Services involve the (co-)production, transfer, and use of tailored climate information products to improve decision-making at different scales (Vaughan and Dessai, 2014).
Value	The word 'value' has been defined as the range of benefits (economic and/or non-economic) that can be gained from using climate information in decision-making (Bruno Soares et al., 2018).

4. Acronyms

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 4-1 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
MED-GOLD	Referring to the project entitled “Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems”
RD	Reference documents
WP	Work Package

5. References

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document.

Table 5-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Khosravi, M., Bruno Soares, M. 2021. Summary of the survey questions, rationale, and dissemination.	Deliverable 5.2.		2021
[RD.2]	Khosravi, M., Bruno Soares, M. 2021. Assessment of the added value for the decision-making process for the durum wheat sector	Deliverable 4.4		2021
[RD.3]	Dilling, L., Lemos, M.C., 2011. Creating usable science: opportunities and constraints for climate knowledge use and their implications for science policy. <i>Global Environ. Change</i> 21, 680–689. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.11.006 .			2011
[RD.4]	Bruno Soares M, Alexander M, Dessai S (2018) Sectoral use of climate information in Europe: a synoptic overview. <i>Climate Service</i> 9:5–20.			2018
[RD.5]	Lemos, C.L. Kirchhoff, Ch.J. Ramprasad, V. 2012. Narrowing the climate information usability gap. <i>Nature climate change</i> . DOI: 10.1038/NCLIMATE1614.			2012

6. Assessing the potential usability of the MED-GOLD pilot services in each sector

This deliverable is part of task 5.2 “Engaging, validating and exploiting the pilot services with the MED-GOLD community” whose aim is to engage with the MED-GOLD community in order to share, discuss and evaluate the pilot services developed for the three sectors. In particular, this deliverable reports back on the findings from an online survey which sought to a) engage with the MED- GOLD community regarding the climate services developed in each sector and b) ascertain the potential usability of the pilot services in those organisations. This online survey complements the participatory workshops conducted with other organisations in Europe that are reported in deliverable 5.3. The survey structure and questions have been described in detail in deliverable 5.2. Here, we provide an overview of the survey structure, design and dissemination below.

6.1. Summary of survey structure, design and dissemination

The survey was divided into four distinct sections, including:

Welcome page – This section introduced the project, specified how the data are used and managed (according to the ethical agreement and data protection laws) and briefly explains how the respondent should navigate through the survey.

Section 1: About participants and their organisation – This section captured key details of the organisation, role of the respondents and their sector of interest (Olive, Grape or Durum wheat).

Section 2: Tool demonstration – This section demonstrated the climate service tools (i.e. the Dashboard and Granoduro.net) through videos developed within the MED-GOLD project. Three videos have been prepared to demonstrate the content and functionality of climate services developed within MED-GOLDMED-GOLD.

Section 3: Evaluating the usability of the climate service - This section aimed to identify the potential usability of the pilot services in respondents’ organisations and asked participants to provide any recommendations on increasing the usability of the tool.

Section 4: Identifying external factors – This final section attempted to identify the external factors that may limit the use of the tool in the organisation and any further comments that the respondent may feel are relevant.

The final version of the survey was developed using the software package Survey Monkey. The survey was tested with project partners in April 2021 and the participants were asked to test the pilot version and provide their feedback and comments on how to further refine the survey. It was then translated from English into Italian, Spanish, and Portuguese to ensure a wider participation across Europe. These languages were

selected as they represent the most common languages spoken in the MED-GOLD community. The translated versions of the survey were integrated into the software ready for dissemination.

The survey was launched on 1st of June 2021 through sending the survey link to the MED-GOLD community. The MED-GOLD community was the starting point of the dissemination. In order to maximise survey responses, various dissemination strategies were followed, such as:

- MED-GOLD partners were asked to circulate the survey to their professional networks and other relevant initiatives.
- The survey link was added to the MED-GOLD website;
- The MED-GOLD Twitter account was used to disseminate the survey;
- Relevant initiatives and companies were identified and asked to complete the survey.

The progress of the survey was monitored at periodic intervals to check the target dissemination activities. Reminders were also circulated after the first 4 weeks (1st of July) and again 2 weeks before the closing date (15th August).

6.2. Survey Results

6.2.1. Participants, their organisation and use of climate information

We received a total of **174 responses**. The majority of respondents were from the private sector (n=94, 56%) and research institutions (n=31, 18%). Remaining respondents were from government agencies/departments, NGOs, international agencies, and other sectors (figure 6.1.).

Figure 6.1: Survey respondents per type of organisation

The organisations represented in the survey were largely based in Spain (n=60, 35.9%), Portugal (n=36, 21.5%), and Italy (n=32, 19.1%), which is perhaps not surprising as that's where the MED-GOLD case studies were pursued (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2: Participants responses based on their organisations' location

In terms of the primary role of respondents, most identified themselves as managers (n=40, 23.8%), researchers (n=35, 20.8%) and agronomists (n=33, 19.6%). Other roles included farmers (n=22, 13.1%), consultants (n=12, 7.1%) and policy makers (n=6, 3.6%) (figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3: Primary role of participants

Participants were asked whether they currently use climate information in their role. A total of **139** reported using climate information to support their role. These participants are referred as the '**user group**' in this report. The user group utilised climate information over a range of timescales to perform their roles, such as

historical climate information, weather information, seasonal forecasts and climate change projections. Figure 6.4 shows that weather and historical climate information are the most frequent timescales used by users in their activities and decision-making processes.

Figure 6.4: Number of respondents per types of climate information used

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

Survey findings also show that various types of variables are used by participants with precipitation (average), temperature (average) and temperature (maximum) being the most commonly used data by survey participants. Less frequently used variables include wind speed and direction, particularly regarding seasonal forecasts and climate change projections (figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5: Weather and climate variables used by respondents

A total of 35 participants considered themselves as 'non-users' of climate information. These 'non-users' were asked to rate the main reasons for not using climate information, which are illustrated in figure 6.6. For most respondents, the main reason for not using climate information was that it was not required to perform their current role (n=16). Other reasons included a lack of in-house expertise to process climate information (n=8), as well as the view that climate information is not currently provided in a form that is useful for users' needs (n=3).

Figure 6.6: Reasons for not using climate information by non-users

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

6.2.2. Demonstration of the Tools

In this section of the survey, respondents were asked to select their sector of interest: Olive and olive oil; Grape and wine or Durum wheat and pasta. They were then able to watch the relevant tool demonstration video – the Dashboard or Granoduro.net - and directed to relevant sector specific questions. A total of 148 respondents answered this section. As figure 6.7 shows, 70 respondents selected Grape and wine sector (47%), 52 of them selected Olive and olive oil sector (35%) and 26 selected Durum wheat and pasta (18%).

Figure 6.7: Number of the survey participants per sector

6.2.3. Assessing the potential usability of the Dashboard in the olive oil sector

A total of 52 respondents reported using climate information and indices to support their current role in the Olive sector. When asked what climate information they usually need in their current role, respondents (n=40) stated that historical data, weather and seasonal forecasts are the most important (Figure 6.8). These participants were asked about the kind of climate indices they need for their activities. Thirty-one participants responded and identified Total precipitation (Oct-May) and Total annual precipitation as the most practical climatic indices required (which supports findings from the users' needs assessment in Olive sector summarised in deliverable 2.1.). The number of days with maximum temperature in spring (Apr-May) was the third most important index, which could be important for plant treatment and irrigation to reinforce plants against extreme temperatures and hydrologic stress. However, it is important to note that all indices presented to respondents were considered relatively important (Figure 6.9).

Figure 6.8: The type of weather and climate information users need to support their key decisions in olive sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

Figure 6.9: Types of climate indices users need in the Olive and olive oil sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected) (n=31)

Figure 6.10 shows the reasons for respondents to use these types of climate information/indices in their role. Climate information is used because it is thought to improve the quality of decision-making (n=23), as well

as being deemed necessary for the respondents' role (n=23). Few responded that it is part of the policy, company or industry regulation to apply climate information in their decision-making (n=5 in both cases).

Figure 6.10: The reason for using climate information by users in Olive sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

To explore the saliency aspect of the tool, participants were asked about the tool's accessibility, understandability, climate variables and their lead time. Regarding the tool's accessibility, 40 participants responded to this question and 25 of them agreed or strongly agreed that the tool is easy to use (figure 6.11).

Figure 6.11: Participants responses to the tool accessibility

We also asked them whether the information provided by the tool is easy to interpret and/or understand. Forty participants answered the question and 25 of them agreed or strongly agreed that the information provided by the tool is easy to understand (Figure 6.12).

Figure 6.12: Participants responses to the tool understandability in Olive sector

They were then asked whether the Dashboard provides the right timescales to inform different decisions in their role. 26 out of 39 responded and agreed that the tool provides information on appropriate timescales for their roles (Figure 6.13).

Figure 6.13: Participants responses to the right timescales available on the Dashboard

We also asked them whether the tool provides the weather and climate variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in their sector. Forty participants responded and 25 agreed that the tool provides the variables that they need to make decisions in their roles (Figure 6.14).

Figure 6.14: Participants responses to the right variable available on the Dashboard

More importantly, we asked them about the reliability of the information provided by the Dashboard (i.e., if the information is trustworthy). Forty respondents answered this question and 24 of them were sure that data seem reliable, and fourteen participants were not sure whether data are reliable or not (Figure 6.15).

Figure 6.15: Participants responses to the reliability of the data on the Dashboard

Most respondents were of the opinion that climate information could help them in several decisions such as those related to pest control (n=29), irrigation (n=27), harvest planning (n=25) and fertilization (n=25) (Figure 6.16).

Figure 6.16: Types of decisions that data on the Dashboard could help respondents with

Regarding the potential benefits that respondents could have from applying the Dashboard in their activities these were largely related to the ability to better manage pest control. The information can help them plan the amount of product they need for plant treatment (figure 6.17).

Figure 6.17: Types of benefits that can be yielded from using the data from the Dashboard

We also asked respondents to rate whether the tool could add value into their activities (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**8). Thirty-two respondents agreed that use of the information could support their decisions, especially in the growing season and harvesting period.

Figure 6.18: Participants responses to using Dashboard could add value to their decision-making

Most users in the Olive oil sector (n=33) said they would use the tool in the future. Six respondents were not sure whether they would use the tool in the future (Figure 6.19).

Figure 6.19: Using the dashboard in the future

We also asked respondents whether they would recommend the dashboard to others e.g. technicians and farmers, to support their activities and decision-making (e.g. pest treatment, fertilization). Thirty-one respondents (75%) agreed that they would recommend the tool to other users (figure 6.20).

Figure 6.20: Participants responses to whether they recommend the tool to other users

The next question discerns some recommendations to make the Dashboard more useful as follows:

- **Improving access and management of it:** Although many respondents agreed that the tool is easy to access, this section revealed calls for easily accessible information.
- **Updating the information automatically:** The dashboard should be an operational tool with climate data updated periodically,
- **Language, map improvements:** Adding Spanish language to the tool could increase its usability as the tool was designed in English and it limited the use of tool by Spanish farmers. They also commented that the current version of the dashboard is only usable for technical users and it is too technical for farmers and non-technical users.

6.2.4. Assessing the potential usability of the Dashboard in the wine sector

Findings from the survey (n=34) shows that different types of climate information are being used in the wine sector. However, weather data is the most commonly used type of information in the wine sector to support users' roles and activities. This result is in line with findings from task 3.4 where SOGRAPE interviewees stated they mostly use weather information for short-term planning activities such as treatments decisions and harvest timing (see deliverable 3.4.). However, other types of climate information are being used by survey respondents such as seasonal forecasts, historical climate information and climate projections (Figure 6.21).

Figure 6.21: Types of weather and climate information users need to support their key decisions in the wine sector

The participants were also asked about the type of climate indices they need in their activities or role to inform key decisions. Forty four out of 70 (62%) users responded to this question and their responses show numbers of heat stress days (n=38), spring total precipitation (n=37) and growing season temperature (n=35) are the most important climate indices in the wine sector (Figure 6.22).

Figure 6.22: Various climate indices' needs in the Wine sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

We also asked respondents to rate the main reasons for using climate information/impact indicators (as illustrated in Figure 6.23). Forty four out of 70 (62%) users responded to this question. Most respondents required climate information to perform their current roles (n=28), but some other reasons also emerged.

Using climate information can improve the quality of decision making (n=24), as well as the view that it is company policy to use climate information as a response to climate change (n=16).

Figure 6.23: Reasons for using climate information by users in the Wine sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

Regarding saliency aspects of the Dashboard, such as its accessibility, most respondents agreed that the tool is easy to access and only 5% (n=2) were of the opinion that it is not accessible easily. Nine of them (22%) were not sure if it is easily accessible or not (figure 6.24).

Figure 6.24: Participants responses to the tool's accessibility

We asked them whether the information provided by the tool is easy to interpret or understand. Forty participants answered to the question and 32 of them agreed or strongly agreed that the tool is easy to understand (Figure 6.25).

Figure 6.25: Participants responses to the tool understandability

Respondents were asked to rate the temporal resolution of the data available on the Dashboard in terms of meeting their current needs. Forty participants replied and 28 agreed or strongly agreed that the timescales of the information provided was sufficient to support their activities (even though the Dashboard does not provide weather information which is the type of information most needed in the sector– see figure 6.21).

Figure 6.26: Participants responses to the right timescales available on the Dashboard

They were questioned whether the Dashboard provides the climate variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in the wine sector. Forty-one participants responded and 32 agreed or strongly agreed that

the tool provides the variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in their roles (Figure 6.27). They were further questioned whether these data seemed reliable for them to use in their decisions. Most respondents (82%) agreed or strongly agreed that the data seems reliable to use in their roles and only 8 of them (18%) were not sure whether data are reliable or not (Figure 6.28).

Figure 6.27: Participants responses to Dashboard providing the variables they need

Figure 6.28: Participants responses to the reliability of the data on the Dashboard

We asked what types of decisions the Dashboard could help the participants with. As Figure 6.29 shows, there is a consensus that the tool could help support specific decisions such as harvest planning (n=37), pest control (n=35) and long-term decisions like vineyard investment (n=27). Others also stated that the Dashboard could help with other decisions such as disease control, phytosanitary treatments. Comments provided by respondents included:

- The dashboard could help us with short-term decisions such as harvest planning and pest control, and long-term decisions such as future investments;

- The data provided by the dashboard are very useful to plan the most appropriate cultural activities throughout the growing season; e.g., it helps me to predict the amount and type of products I need for my vineyard for the following season;
- Weather data (historical and ahead) is fundamental to prevent fungus diseases and harvest dates decision. Moreover, as well as future vineyard investments;
- Optimize treatment dates and help reduce the number of treatments. Have values that help us to understand the evolution of the vegetative cycle and, consequently, help in the decision of works such as the beginning of the harvest;
- Better harvest planning, e.g., it could help me to decide how many labourers I need for harvest or determine appropriate time to contract with labourers and so on;
- Disease control, preventive practices against heat stroke, decision making on setting the harvest dates;
- Phytosanitary issues, prevention of scald and/or weather accidents (hail, frost, ...), state of maturity and harvest date.

Figure 6.29: Participants responses to the types of decision that data on the Dashboard could help with

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

We finally asked what changes they would recommend to increase the usability of the Dashboard. Only 3 participants provided comments to this question:

- To make it [the Dashboard] easier to use;
- To develop it for other crops;

- We need more variables according to region of Chile, we work in a system to remote monitoring grape crops, the target are producers of table grape in this moment; they are interested in quality control.

6.2.5. Assessing the potential usability of Granoduro.net in the durum wheat sector

Of the 148 interviewees who claimed that they use climate information in their role, 26 (18%) were from the durum wheat sector. The user group in this sector were questioned regarding what kind of timescales they need in their activities in the sector. The results show that weather information and seasonal forecasts are most frequently used in this sector but climate projections are less important (Fig 6.30). This result was endorsed by participants of the previous assessment which was done in Task 4.4, where they stated that they usually use weather and seasonal forecasts for decisions such as choice of wheat variety, sowing date, fertilisation, crop protection, harvest and even for making contracts.

Figure 6.30: Participants responses to timescales needs in Durum wheat Sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

Participants were asked about the type of climate indicators they need in their roles or activities. Their responses show that heat stress and cold stress, hydrological balance are important indices (Fig 6.31) which aligns with the results from the users' needs assessment conducted in task 4.4 (RD.2).

Figure 6.31: Participants responses to climate indicators' needs in Durum wheat Sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

We also asked respondents to rate their reasons for using climate information in their roles. As figure 6.32 shows, for most respondents climate information was used because it can improve the quality of decision-making (n=10) and/or is vital for performing their roles (n=10). However, other reasons also emerged including industry regulations (n=5) and company policy to use climate information as part of a climate change strategy (n=6).

Figure 6.32: Participants responses to the reasons for using climate data in Durum wheat Sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

Participants were also asked about the saliency of the tool in terms of its accessibility and 15 out of 21 agreed or strongly agreed that the tool is easy to access (Figure 6.33). We also asked them whether it is easy to understand and interpret the information provided in Granoduro.net. Most of the participants (n=14) agreed or strongly agreed that the data on the tool are understandable (Figure 6.34). Only one of the 22 participants disagreed with this statement.

Figure 6.33: Participants responses to the tool's accessibility

Figure 6.34: Participants responses to the tool's understandability

Participants were asked whether the tool Granoduro.net provided the climate variables and indicators that they need to make decisions in the durum wheat sector. Twenty-two participants responded and 14 out of 22 agreed or strongly that the tool provides the variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in their roles. Only 2 of them believed that the tool does not provide all the information to support their decisions (Figure 6.35). They were also questioned about the important aspect of data usability which is reliability of the information provided by the tool. Twenty-one users responded to this and 12 of them agreed that the data seem reliable but nine participants were not sure whether the data are reliable or not (Figure 6.36).

Figure 6.35: Participants responses to Ganoduro.net providing the variables they need in their roles

Figure 6.36: Participants responses to the to the tool data' reliability in durum sector

The participants were further questioned about type of decisions they think Granoduro.net could help them with. Nineteen participants responded to this question and stated that the tool could help them with decisions such as variety choice (n=15), fertilization (n=14), and crop protection (n=14). This is in line with the result of usability assessment which was done during task 4.4, where most respondents were of the opinion that

the tool could help them in some decisions especially crop protection and fertilization in the growing season. Nevertheless, some respondents chose decisions such as soil tillage (n=8) and weeding (n=9) (Figure 6.37).

Figure 6.37: Type of decisions which could be supported by the tool in durum wheat sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

They were asked about the potential benefits of using the tool in their roles. Twenty participants answered and most thought that the tool could help them with better disease control (n=15) and improve efficiency in their crop protection planning, especially with using climatic indices (n=14) (Figure 6.38).

Figure 6.38: Participants responses to the potential benefits of the tool in wheat Sector

(*note that multiple answers could be selected)

We then followed up by asking them to explain how the information provided by Granoduro.net could support them in the decisions they selected in the previous question. Very few participants provided comments:

- “Besides knowing the number of nitrogen units on the base of the forecast, I can understand when to distribute them”.
- “It allows me to know the risk forecasted for the season”.
- “Information on phenology helps me provide the amplitude of the time interval for doing fertilisation. The risk on diseases helps me plan the crop protection interventions months ahead.
- The climatological indexes help me in the choice of the type of fertiliser to apply by observing the hydrological balance in the different phase. Thus, proving a forecast on the amount of water arriving on the ground as rain”.

Overall, respondents believed using the tool could add value to their decision-making, hence, they stated they would use it in the future (Figure 6.39). Nevertheless, we asked them what changes they would make to increase the usability of Granoduro.net and a smaller number of respondents provided comments:

- Automatic data entry from agriculture 4.0 data and Platform,
- Introduce a service guiding the farmer in the choice of soil tillage before sowing, taking into account the preceding crop,
- Choice of timing for fertilisation or for sprays,
- Multi language availability,
- Choice of type of fertilisers based on the market offers and the other information already listed, such as variety etc,
- Actual application of 4.0 agriculture in the farms subject of the disciplinary, so to the data update is in real time and to create alerts for the users.

Figure 6.39: Participants responses to the future use of the tool in wheat sector decision-making

6.2.6. External factors

As a final question, we asked respondents to rate the following external factors which can potentially act as barriers for them to be able to use the information provided by the MED-GOLD pilot services. Eighty-four responded to this question. Based on participants' responses, there are no strong barriers potentially hindering their use of these tools. However, insufficient in-house human or technical support in their organisations to use seasonal forecast or climate projections, misconceptions and lack of trust on climate information accuracy and lack of awareness about the benefits of using climate forecasts in decision-making were perceived as potential barriers to the use of the information provided by the tools. Government regulations (such as legal requirements) was perceived as the least [important?] potential factor to act as a barrier to the use of climate information. As such, efforts on training activities, raising awareness exercises and increasing in-house capacity can help overcome some of these barriers and help increase the tools' usability.

Table 6-1 Rate of external factors as the main barriers for using the climate services

External factors	0 No barrier		1 Very mild		2 mild		3 Moderate		4 Strong		5 Very strong	
	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n
Insufficient legal requirements to uptake seasonal forecasts	53%	45	4.8%	4	13%	11	19%	16	6%	5	3.5%	3
Insufficient in-house human to use seasonal forecasts or projections in the organisation,	27%	23	15.3%	13	14%	12	21%	18	13%	11	9.4%	8
Lack of awareness about the benefits of climate forecasts in decision-making,	34%	29	14.3%	12	18%	15	16%	14	10%	8	7%	6
Lack of willingness in your organisation to use seasonal forecasts,	40%	34	13.1%	11	19.9%	16	16.6%	14	7.9%	6	3.3%	3
Misconception (lack of trust) of climate information' inaccuracy among farmers.	23%	20	10.5%	9	18.8%	16	24.7%	21	12.9%	11	9.9%	8

6.3. Conclusions

This deliverable reports the result of task 5.2 which aims to engage with the MED-GOLD community to assess the pilot services developed for the three sectors as well as provide feedback to those services. In doing so, we designed an online survey and disseminate it to the MED-GOLD community. In total, we received 174 responses, representing the views of current users (n=139) and non-users (n=35) of climate information and impact indicators. The majority of respondents represented the private sector (n=94, 56%) and research institutions (n=31, 18%) and in terms of their primary role, most identified themselves as managers (n=40, 23.8%), researchers (n=35, 20.8%) and agronomists (n=33, 19.6%). To participate in the assessment, respondents were asked to watch the tool videos and then be directed to the relevant sector specific questions. 70 respondents selected Grape and wine sector (47%), 52 of them selected Olive and olive oil sector (35%) and 26 selected Durum wheat (18%).

In the olive sector, respondents all agreed the dashboard provides the timescales and variables they need in their decision-making. They also discussed that the tool could help them with some critical decisions such

as pest control, harvest planning and estimation of production. In terms of data reliability, they all believed the data are reliable enough to use it in their role. However, they highlighted that the tool language can limit its usability by end-users such as farmers and they believed that adding Spanish language to the tool is vital. They also commented that the current version of the dashboard is only suitable for technical users and it is too technical for farmers and non-technical users. Therefore, more simplification and training are required especially for non-technical users. They also commented that the operational version of the tool needs to be updated periodically. These results are exactly in line with the added value assessment which was done with end-users who were directly involved in the co-development of the tool in Task 2.4.

In the wine sector, most respondents agreed that the dashboard is salient enough as it provides climate information on appropriate timescales to support their short term decision-making such as harvest planning and pest control, as well as long term decisions such as future investments. They were of the opinion that the data provided by the dashboard are useful to plan the most appropriate cultural activities throughout the growing season, e.g., predicting the amount and type of products they need for their vineyard for the following season, harvest planning, disease control and preventing of scald and/or weather accidents like frost. However, when it comes to recommendations, they suggested the dashboard should be easier to use. This final result confirmed the result of the tool's added value assessment in task 3.4 where half of the participants stated that the tool was not intuitive enough and there is a need for simplification.

In the durum wheat sector, in terms of saliency, the respondents agreed that Granoduro.net is accessible, and provides information over timescales they need in their roles. Most of them think that the tool could help them with better disease control, improve efficiency in their crop protection planning especially with using indices. For example, by observing the hydrological balance in the different phase of growth cycle of durum wheat, they choose the most suitable type of fertiliser. In response to recommendations on increasing the tool's usability, they believe that a multi-language version could be helpful. However, assessing usable information isn't limited to internal factors such as saliency, credibility and legitimacy. External factors include organizational constraints, lack of human resources, or lack of political factors which can hinder application of usable climate information in the decision-making process and adaptation planning (Dilling and Lemos., 2011; Bruno Soares et al. 2018; Lemos et al., 2012). Therefore, to complete the assessment, we asked participants about these external factors. The results showed that insufficient in-house human or technical support within an organisation to use seasonal forecast or climate projections, misconception of the accuracy of climate information among users and lack of awareness about the benefit of using climate forecasts in decision-making are the main external factors that could act as a barrier to use the information provided by the tools.

